

Dynamic Schedule Computation for Time-Aware Shaper in Converged IoT-Cloud Environments

George Papathanail, Ilias Sakellariou, Lefteris Mamatas, and Panagiotis Papadimitriou

University of Macedonia, Greece

{papathanail, iliass, emamatas, papadimitriou}@uom.edu.gr

Abstract—Over the last years, we have seen the emergence of (hyper-)distributed applications, which tend to be provisioned over resources that span IoT devices, IoT gateways, and compute nodes from edge computing infrastructures. The deployment and orchestration of such services benefits from types of IoT middleware, known as Virtual Objects (VOs). However, in order to reap the benefits of VOs, low-latency communication is required between the IoT devices and their associated VOs.

To this end, we utilize Time-Sensitive Networking (TSN), which has paved the way for the timely delivery of delay-sensitive traffic. Our main contribution lies in the design and evaluation of a TSN scheduler, which is compliant with the Time-Aware Shaper (TAS). In this respect, we present a constraint programming formulation for the TSN scheduling problem at hand. A salient feature of the proposed TSN scheduler is its ability to compute the schedule periods both efficiently and at small time-scales. The latter is of crucial importance for dynamic conditions, where the association of IoT devices and their virtual counterparts is subject to change.

I. INTRODUCTION

Deterministic networking (DetNet) has evolved as a crucial need for a wide range of application domains, such as industrial networks, automotive communications, mobile wireless networks, and service provider networks [1]–[7]. DetNet, in particular, aims at sustaining bounded latency and jitter, low packet loss, and high reliability for a subset of flows with stringent latency and/or throughput requirements. As such, the data of delay-sensitive flows can be delivered within certain deadlines, which becomes critical in *e.g.*, converged Internet-of-Things (IoT) and cloud infrastructures, where IoT devices need to establish low-latency communication either with application components or their digital twins.

In this respect, DetNet has attracted significant attention and is evolving rapidly under the auspices of various working groups (*e.g.*, IETF DETNET and IEEE 802.1 Time-Sensitive Networking – TSN) [6]. The former encompasses a set of standards and mechanisms for deterministic QoS, such as explicit routes, end-to-end synchronization, packet replication and elimination. On the other hand, IEEE 802.1 TSN has introduced a wide range of techniques for time synchronization (802.1 AS [8]), traffic scheduling (802.1 Qbv [9]), frame preemption (802.1 Qbu [10]), asynchronous traffic shaping (802.1 Qcr), and stream reservation (802.1 Qcc [11]), among others.

Although DetNet/TSN are evolving as an indispensable ingredient of network infrastructures for the needs of various application domains, in this work, we particularly focus on emerging IoT-cloud environments, which are characterized by the convergence of IoT and edge/cloud computing technologies. Such environments tend to utilize IoT platforms in the form of middlewares to augment the interaction between IoT devices and application components, often deployed on cloud infrastructures. This notion of IoT middleware can be incarnated through the so-called Virtual Objects (VOs) that essentially comprise virtual counterparts of either a single or a cluster of IoT devices [12]. A VO can execute generic or device-specific functions for data processing and fusion, alleviating the computational burden of IoT devices and also reducing their energy consumption, which is of crucial importance for battery-operated IoT devices. Furthermore, VOs can facilitate the representation and management of (clusters of) IoT devices through unified abstractions, whereas, at the same time, they can pave the way for tackling various convergence and interoperability aspects.

Such VOs will be instantiated in edge cloud facilities, preferably in proximity to the IoT devices that they are associated with. For instance, IoT devices can be connected to an IoT gateway to establish connectivity with the network infrastructure, and, more specifically, with a proximate edge cloud that hosts the VOs in the form of containers. Nevertheless, an optimized VO placement cannot guarantee on its own certain bounds on latency and jitter for the communication between any IoT device and its respective VO. We stress on the need for IoT/VO low-latency communication, since any latency inflation (*i.e.*, due to interference with other traffic) can introduce implications (*e.g.*, high response time) on applications that interact with IoT devices through VOs or can hinder the synchronization in data acquisition processes from multiple devices.

Along these lines, there is a pressing need for time-sensitive communication among IoT devices and VOs to meet the KPIs of applications, provisioned over resources that span IoT devices, IoT gateways, and compute nodes at edge cloud facilities. To this end, we employ TSN, and in particular, the IEEE 802.1 Qbv based mechanism [9], known as Time-Aware Shaper (TAS), to sustain bounded latency and jitter between communicating IoT devices and their virtualized counterparts (*i.e.*, VOs). A significant challenge here lies in the dynamic

computation of TSN schedules, which, in the context of TAS, correspond to Gate Control List (GCL) configurations.

In essence, a TSN schedule engine should derive the number of queues required and compute the transmission periods for each traffic class across all TSN bridges that reside in the path between each IoT-VO pair. To this end, we present a constraint programming formulation, whose solver is benchmarked against static TSN schedules using simulations conducted on OMNeT++. The proposed TAS schedule computation mechanism can be integrated into fully centralized or hybrid TSN control plane platforms [3], [7], [13], which we plan to investigate in future work.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. In Section II, we lay out the notion of VO and highlight its role for the convergence of IoT and edge/cloud computing platforms. Section III serves as a primer for TSN with emphasis on TAS (that we adopt in this work) and existing control plane approaches. In Section IV, we elaborate on our constraint programming formulation for the TAS schedule computation. In Section V, we present simulation results in order to validate the proposed TAS schedule engine and quantify the potential gains, compared to static TSN schedules for IoT traffic prioritization. Section VI provides an overview of related work, whereas Section VII highlights our conclusions and provides directions for future work.

II. VIRTUAL OBJECT

A Virtual Object (VO) refers to a digital representation of an IoT physical device. A VO resides and operates either on an edge cloud or on a far-edge device. We could argue that VO acts as intelligent middleware, effectively bridging the gap between the IoT device and the application that operates at the edge or a core cloud infrastructure. A high-level representation of a VO is illustrated in Fig. 1. VOs offer a high degree of flexibility and can execute device-specific, as well as generic functionalities. This implies that they have the ability to replicate and enhance the functionalities of IoT devices, while also offering shared functions across all devices, such as data aggregation [12]. At the same time, a VO can open up opportunities for distributed intelligence, since AI-assisted resource management and orchestration operations for the network (far-)edge can be potentially realized within VOs, offloading centralized orchestrators.

From the perspective of the client, the VO is considered an integral component of an application graph. As such, a VO can realize various application-related functionalities, such as accessing data from IoT devices or implementing actions on these devices. The VO is orchestratable, as part of the application graph and, thus, can be managed, monitored, scaled, and migrated.

The establishment of low-latency communication between IoT devices and their corresponding VOs is an essential necessity in order to fulfill the diverse and stringent application-related Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), such as low latency. The integration of VO with TSN can improve the efficiency and reliability of real-time communication between

Fig. 1: Virtual Object.

IoT devices and the application. The deterministic nature of TSN guarantees accurate and predictable transmission of data.

III. TIME-SENSITIVE NETWORKING

TSN consists of mechanisms for transmitting data with a high level of criticality over Ethernet that exhibit deterministic behavior. Most TSN projects primarily build upon the IEEE 802.1Q standards, which pertain to Bridges and Bridged Networks. These standards specifically address the implementation of Virtual Local Area Networks (VLAN) and network switches. The purpose of these enhancements is to facilitate the transfer of data with bounded latency and high reliability [1], [3], [14]. TSN is especially pertinent in domains such as automotive and industrial control, where converged networks are utilized for real-time audio/video streaming and control streams.

A. Time-Aware Shaper

In the domain of IEEE 802.1 standards, 802.1 Qbv (also known as Time-Aware Shaper) introduces the concept of a transmission gate operation for each queue associated with a specific traffic class (Fig. 2). At the egress port of a TSN bridge, outgoing frames pass through a Traffic Classification block that assigns distinct streams to their corresponding traffic classes. During T1, the traffic class 0, which has been designated with a traffic priority of 0, is available for transmission. The packets are subsequently organized into different traffic classes according to the state of the transmission gates. More specifically, the gates can have two possible states, *i.e.*, open or closed, and their operational status is regulated by a Gate Control List (GCL). A GCL comprises numerous schedule entries for each output port, enabling the forwarding of selected traffic through open gates to the transmission selection block, which grants access to the medium. For a TSN switch equipped with IEEE 802.1 Qbv schedules to operate effectively, the clocks of all switches must be synchronized. This would guarantee that all TSN switches consistently refer to the same cycle base time in their schedules. Such synchronization can be accomplished by the utilization of the Precision Time Protocol (PTP). 802.1 Qbv combined with PTP can effectively empower the reliable

transmission of high-priority traffic without being disrupted by other low-priority or best-effort traffic.

B. TSN Control Plane

The TSN control plane model operates as an interface between the Talker-Listener pairs and the TSN network, enabling the transmission of stream requirements to the network without necessitating awareness of the network’s particular attributes. The control plane model facilitates the setup of TSN bridges by utilizing topology-specific information and the capabilities of the TSN network, in conjunction with the stream requirements. This empowers the deterministic communication between pairs of Talkers and Listeners, guaranteeing that the transmission of data streams is not adversely affected by factors such as latency, jitter, and other network-related factors.

To this end, the IEEE 802.1 Qcc [11] amendment has proposed three TSN control plane models, namely (i) *Fully Distributed*, (ii) *Hybrid* and (iii) *Fully Centralized*, each one with its own unique characteristics and benefits. These models provide the means for managing the TSN network and ensuring the reliable and efficient delivery of data streams between Talker-Listener pairs. According to the *Fully Distributed* model, the user requirements from the end-stations are communicated throughout the entire network topology using a distributed protocol. The User-Network Interface (UNI) is situated between the end-stations and the Bridge to which they are connected in the topology. In the *Hybrid* case, the control plane is based on the concept of centralized network control and distributed user model. More precisely, it encompasses a centralized network controller, referred to as the Centralized Network Configurator (CNC), that maintains complete knowledge of the network architecture and the specifications of the data streams. The CNC is responsible for configuring TSN features and executing complex tasks, such as computing TSN schedules, managing reservation mechanisms, scheduling streams, enabling Frame Preemption, specifically at the TSN bridges. Finally, the *Fully Centralized* model includes a Centralized User Configurator (CUC) that connects with both the CNC and end devices. The end-stations send flow-specific requirements to a CNC. Subsequently, CUC places a request for deterministic communication to the CNC, based on the requirements previously conveyed from talker/listeners.

IV. TSN SCHEDULING

The TSN scheduling problem is considered as NP-complete. Several approaches have been proposed to tackle this problem, such as Satisfiability Modulo Theories (SMT) [5], [15], Constraint Programming [16], Heuristics [17], [18], and Genetic Algorithms [19]. In terms of TSN schedule computation, the main objective is to determine a feasible scheduling pattern for incoming flows with respect to their specified requirements (e.g., latency, jitter), based on a defined model and constraints. The scheduling model in our work is built on the principles of constraint programming, due to its ability to provide flexibility

Fig. 2: Gate Control List in IEEE 802.1 Qbv.

in terms of problem modeling and effective heuristic search combined with robust constraint propagation techniques.

We follow a similar approach to modeling the TSN scheduling problem in constraint programming, as those in [20], [5], [21]. Thus, we assume the usual graph representation found in [20], to represent the network, i.e., we consider a graph $G = (V, E)$, where vertices (nodes n_i) are either switches or end-points, whereas edges are links ($l_{ij} \in E$) connecting the former, i.e., link l_{ij} connects nodes i and j respectively. Each link l_{ij} is characterized by its propagation delay $d_{l_{ij}}$, its speed sp_{ij} , and several queues Q_{ij} that are at most 8 according to IEEE 802.1 Qbv [9]. Switches also have a processing (or fabric) delay sd_i which is constant.

In the current setting, we consider a set of periodic flows F of single packets (frames), i.e., the payload of each flow can fit into a single Ethernet frame, where each flow $f_k \in F$, has a deadline df_k , a packet size p_k , a period T_k that determines the frequency of the transmission, and is associated with a valid path P^k , that consists of an ordered list of links $[l_{t_i}, l_{i_j}, \dots, l_{n_l}]$ from the transmitting end-point n_t , i.e., the *talker*, to the receiving end-point n_l (i.e., the *listener*).

The problem can be considered as a classic job-shop scheduling problem, where each flow transmission is considered as a *task*, consisting of as many transmission *operations* as the links it traverses along the path to the listener, with several additional constraints that will be discussed below. Thus, a flow f_k on a path P_k of length N can be modeled as a set of operations $1..N$, each having a start time (offset) relative to the start of the schedule (time point 0), i.e., the set $\{S_{1,i,j}^k, S_{2,j,k}^k, \dots, S_{N,k,l}^k\}$ where each variable $S_{x,i,j}^k$ represents the start time of the transmission of the packet of flow k on the link l_{i_j} . We define this set as the *primary flow*, for reasons explained later in this section. Additionally, for each flow f_k we define a queue Q_k , which is considered to be the same for all links of the flow.

Scheduling of flows that have different periods occurs in a time domain defined by the *hyperperiod* [5], where the latter is defined as the least common multiple of all flow periods, *i.e.*, $HP = lcm(T_k | f_k \in F)$, thus flows may occur multiple times in a hyperperiod. In the latter case, each flow f_k that occurs $M = HP/T_i$ times in the hyperperiod, consists of $N * M$ start times, as indicated in Eq. (1):

$$f_k = \{S_{1,i,j}^k, \dots, S_{N,k,l}^k, \\ S_{N+1,i,j}^k, \dots, S_{2*N,k,l}^k, \\ \dots \\ S_{N*(M-1)+1,i,j}^k, \dots, S_{M*N,k,l}^k\} \quad (1)$$

We define subflows $S_{x,i,j}^k | x > N$ as *secondary flows* (mentioned as flow occurrences in [20]); we make this distinction since primary flow start time variables and, those of the secondary flow, participate in different constraint in the model. In the CP model, the decision variables are the start times in both primary and secondary flows and the flow's queue, *i.e.*, $\langle \{S_{o,i,j}^k \in [0..HP] | o \in 1..N*M\}, Q_k \in [1..7] \rangle$. The domain of Q_k is restricted to the range [1..7], since queue 0 is reserved for unscheduled best-effort traffic.

Decision variables in the primary and secondary flows are linked by the requirement for zero jitter, which dictates that the time difference in corresponding variables in each secondary subflow should obey the constraint in Eq. (2):

$$\forall n \in 1..N, m \in 2..M, \forall l_{ij} \in P_k \\ S_{n,i,j}^k + (m-1) * T_k = S_{N*(m-1)+n,i,j}^k \quad (2)$$

The first scheduling constraint imposes an *ordering* among the start times of each operation in a task, ensuring that a packet on link l_{ij} has arrived on node n_j , before being transmitted over the link l_{jl} . Enforcement of the constraint occurs only on decision variables of the primary flow and is depicted in Eq. (3). There is no need to define the constraint for secondary flows, due to the equality constraints of Eq. (2), which ensure that the adequate time distance is maintained among operations of each subflow.

$$\forall f_k \in F, \forall o \in 1..(N-1), \\ S_{o,i,j}^k + sd_j + dl_{ij} + \lceil \frac{p_k}{sp_{ij}} \rceil \leq S_{o+1,j,l}^k \quad (3)$$

Eq. (3) factors in the propagation delay dl_{ij} of the link, the transmission delay computed as the ceiling of the packet size over the speed of the link $\lceil \frac{p_k}{sp_{ij}} \rceil$, and the switch delay sd_j of the receiving node.

Given that flows have a deadline, the flow's packet must arrive to the listener node n_l over a link l_{ml} before the deadline df_k :

$$\forall f_k \in F, S_{N,m,l}^k + dl_{ml} + \lceil \frac{p_k}{sp_{ml}} \rceil \leq df_k \quad (4)$$

Once more, the deadline constraint is imposed only on the primary flow variables, and equality constraints of Eq. (2) ensure that is enforced for all flows in the hyperperiod.

Each egress link transmits a single packet at each time point, thus, no two transmissions on the same link may overlap, yielding the constraint in Eq. (5):

$$\forall l_{ij} \in E, f_k, f_r \in F | k < r, \forall S_{x,i,j}^k \in f_k, \forall S_{y,i,j}^r \in f_r, \\ S_{x,i,j}^k + dl_{ij} + \lceil \frac{p_k}{sp_{ij}} \rceil \leq S_{y,i,j}^r \\ \vee \\ S_{y,i,j}^r + dl_{ij} + \lceil \frac{p_r}{sp_{ij}} \rceil \leq S_{x,i,j}^k \quad (5)$$

Eq. (5), commonly found in scheduling problems, is handled by the *global constraint disjunctive* [22], with a plethora of dedicated algorithms to efficiently tackle variable domain reductions. Note that Constraint (5) is enforced in all decision variables of both primary and secondary flows.

Finally, since a frame is fully received before being copied to its destination queue and frames are transmitted according to their reception order, it must be ensured that packets addressed to the same egress link, arrive in the correct order when placed in the same egress queue or are forced to be placed in different queues. The latter is referred to as the *frame isolation* constraint and is modeled by the disjunction depicted in Eq. (6):

$$\forall l_{ij} \in E, f_k, f_r \in F | k < r, \forall S_{x,i,j}^k \in f_k, \forall S_{y,i,j}^r \in f_r, \\ ((Q_k = Q_r) \Rightarrow \\ (S_{x,i,j}^k < S_{y,i,j}^r \Leftrightarrow Arr_{x,i}^k < Arr_{y,i}^r) \wedge \\ (S_{x,i,j}^k > S_{y,i,j}^r \Leftrightarrow Arr_{x,i}^k > Arr_{y,i}^r)) \\ \vee \\ Q_k \neq Q_r \quad (6)$$

where $Arr_{x,i}^k$ is the arrival time of the packet of flow f_k at node i , and is given by Eq. (7):

$$Arr_{x,i}^k = S_{x-1,a,i}^k + dl_{ai} + \lceil \frac{p_k}{sp_{ai}} \rceil \quad (7)$$

The definition of $Arr_{y,i}^r$ is similar. If the frames of flows f_k and f_r arrive on the same ingress link, then the link constraints of Eq. (5) ensure that are transmitted in the correct order by imposing a much more restrictive constraint. If frames arrive on different ingress links, then we ensure that the reception of one of the frames is completed before the other, thus, maintaining the order of placing the frames in the queue. This constraint can be easily implemented using *reified constraints*, offered in most CP solvers.

Our implementation of the model described above relies on the ECLiPSe Constraint Logic Programming system [23]. The implementation choice is dictated by the fact that (i) it supports all constraints required by the model, *i.e.*, the *disjunctive* scheduling constraint and reified constraints, (ii) it offers a variety of search strategies and variable/value ordering general heuristics for finding solutions, and (iii) we could easily integrate the model in the context of our evaluation environment,

by generating Gate Control Lists from the solution obtained for OMNeT++ (as well as with TAPRIO for experimentation with TSN in future work).

V. EVALUATION

This section describes our evaluation environment (Section V-A), followed by a discussion on the evaluation results (Section V-B).

A. Evaluation Environment

The validation of our proposed TAS scheduler is conducted on the OMNeT++ v6.0.1 simulation platform, using the INET 4.5.0 framework. All the experiments are executed on a workstation with 3.2GHz CPU and 16GB RAM.

To assess the proposed TSN scheduling model, we utilize three different topologies, as depicted in Fig. 3. All topologies include paths between IoT nodes to VOs, as well as additional communicating nodes responsible for cross traffic. The number of IoT nodes varies between 6 and 12, depending on the topology. In each topology, traffic is forwarded via TSN switches that utilize GCLs at their egress ports to handle traffic prioritization.

Link capacities are set to 100 Mbps, whereas an additional propagation delay ($d_{l_{ij}}$) of $1\mu s$ is introduced as a simulation parameter. Although OMNeT++ does not inherently introduce processing delays on switches, our tests have uncovered an observed processing delay (sd_i) of approximately $1\mu s$. Consequently, we account for this delay in our simulations.

Across all three simulated topologies, the IoT nodes are responsible for generating time-sensitive traffic, which is treated as high-priority (also termed as *scheduled* traffic). The period of all these flows is set to $800\mu s$, which is also considered as the deadline for each flow, thus, ensuring that all packets are delivered to the VO within a cycle. The length of each packet in the scheduled traffic is set to 400 bytes . Scheduled traffic is tagged with Priority Code Point (PCP) value 4 to augment TSN switches with its handling (*i.e.*, as high-priority).

Furthermore, nodes tagged as BE (Fig. 3) serve the purpose of traffic interference, by injecting Best-Effort (BE) traffic towards sink nodes. Each packet of BE traffic has a size of 800 bytes. BE nodes generate traffic at intervals of $10\mu s$, tagged with PCP value of 0.

B. Evaluation Results

We utilize the model of Section IV to derive the GCL schedules and conduct a set of simulations in order to assess the efficiency of the computed schedules for high-priority traffic. For each simulation topology, the search is based on a value ordering heuristic, selecting the minimum value for the start time from each domain, thus, reporting a valid solution, which is not optimized according to some metric. This helps maintain a negligible runtime for schedule computation, *i.e.*, approximately 4 ms with the largest simulated topology.

The main aim of our study is two-fold: (i) to evaluate the levels of jitter and latency on a TSN topology, and (ii) to showcase the practicality of our model's scheduling

(a) Topology 1.

(b) Topology 2.

(c) Topology 3.

Fig. 3: Simulation topologies.

capabilities. As a baseline for evaluations, we rely on static schedules which have been employed by various studies for traffic prioritization (*e.g.*, [1], [7]). In such static scheduling, the high-priority queue is associated with an $800\mu s$ scheduling interval, whereas the best-effort queue is scheduled at $200\mu s$. In the following, we present evaluation results¹ for scheduled (*i.e.*, IoT-VO) traffic from simulations conducted on all three topologies, as shown in Fig. 3.

Figs. 4 and 5 illustrate the measured latency and jitter from the simulations on Topology 1. The proposed scheduler (indicated as *Dynamic_Scheduled* in the following plots) outperforms the static scheduler both in terms of latency and jitter. More precisely, our schedule model yields a median delay of 0.19 ms. The small size of the interquartile range indicates that a significant number of latency values are tightly

¹Results with best-effort traffic are omitted due to space limitations.

Fig. 4: Latency of scheduled traffic on Topology 1.

Fig. 6: Latency of scheduled traffic on Topology 2.

Fig. 5: Jitter of scheduled traffic on Topology 1.

Fig. 7: Jitter of scheduled traffic on Topology 2.

positioned around the median, which indicates a much lower degree of deviation from the median. This combined with the lack of outliers corroborates the superiority of the proposed scheduler, especially in terms of latency bounds which are more significant (than mean values) in the context of TSN. For instance, the latency with the proposed scheduler remains bounded below 0.25 ms (Fig. 4), as opposed to the static schedules that may lead to delays in excess of 0.4 ms.

Similar observations can be drawn with respect to the jitter that the scheduled traffic experiences (Fig. 5). Scheduling traffic with static intervals yields an increase by 80% in the median value of jitter (compared to the proposed scheduler); however, the margin between the two scheduling techniques is even larger in terms of jitter bounds. While the deviation around the mean is barely perceptible for the proposed scheduler, jitter can exceed 0.1 ms with the static schedules.

We now proceed with the discussion of latency (Fig. 6) and jitter (Fig. 7) measurements at Topology 2, which includes additional talkers that generate larger volumes of traffic (both in terms of IoT-VO and BE). The two scheduling methods under

test exhibit similar margins in their performance, compared to the tests at Topology 1. More specifically, the proposed TSN scheduler achieves a notable reduction in the mean values of latency and jitter, compared to the static counterpart. In addition, the deviation around the mean is relatively confined for our scheduler, which can effectively provide guarantees both in terms of latency and jitter (*e.g.*, we observe a latency bound at approximately 0.35 ms).

Finally, we conduct an additional round of simulations over a more complex topology (*i.e.*, Topology 3 in Fig. 3c), which is characterised by a higher interference among the two classes of traffic (*i.e.*, high-priority and BE). Figs. 8 and 9 illustrate the corresponding results for the latency and jitter experienced by the scheduled traffic with both TSN schedule variants (*i.e.*, dynamic and static). The results indicate that the proposed scheduler is less susceptible to interference among the two traffic classes, by sustaining lower latency and jitter both in terms of mean value and upper bound. Instead, the static scheduler exhibits a substantial deviation in the values of

Fig. 8: Latency of scheduled traffic on Topology 3.

Fig. 9: Jitter of scheduled traffic on Topology 3.

latency and jitter, where, for instance, the latency can inflate to more than 0.4 ms on a topology with minimal propagation delay. The scheduled traffic suffers even more in terms of jitter (Fig. 9), when the static scheduler is in use. It can be observed that even the mean jitter value is substantially higher compared to our scheduler. Apparently, conditions of high interference require dynamically computed schedules in order to alleviate the implications on scheduled traffic.

VI. RELATED WORK

In this section, we provide a brief overview of scheduling techniques for TSN. A survey on scheduling algorithms for TSN is available in [24]. Authors in [5], [25] tackle the TSN scheduling problem by utilizing Satisfiability Modulo Theory (SMT) and Optimization Modulo Theory (OMT) techniques.

The study in [26] investigates the impact of routing time-triggered flows on their capacity to adhere to a schedule. In addition, an Integer Linear Programming (ILP) formulation is proposed to construct predictable routes. Authors in [27] also resort to ILP for addressing the combined routing and scheduling time-triggered traffic problem within the context of Software-Defined Networking (SDN). Vlk, *et al.* [20] address the problem of joint routing and scheduling in a CP setting, proposing two CP models and evaluating mainly the schedulability (*i.e.*, percentage of successful computation of a TSN schedule).

The study in [28] stresses on the need for fast scheduling algorithms in the TSN domain. More specifically, the authors introduce a heuristic scheduler, namely HERMES, designed for time-triggered traffic in TSNs. Authors in [29] introduce a schedulability analysis for the Best-Effort (BE) traffic class in the context of TSNs. The emphasis of this study lies on the BE traffic class, which is commonly used for traffic that does not exhibit stringent delay requirements. Zhao in [30] raises the need for worst-case end-to-end latency analysis in distributed safety-critical applications across various domains, including industrial automation, aerospace, and automotive industries. A delay analysis for AVB traffic is also presented in [31].

A different approach to 802.1 Qbv scheduling is presented in [32]. Specifically, the authors introduce a heuristic scheduler designed for TSNs. This scheduler utilizes a window-based approach, eliminating the need for isolating open gate windows. Machine Learning (ML) based approaches for schedulability analysis on TSNs are introduced in [33], [34]. In particular, the authors employ supervised learning to verify the TSN configurations. Finally, the study in [35] addresses the requirement for real-time communication in the context of Industry 4.0 and intelligent manufacturing facilities. The goal is to create real-time industrial network communication systems.

In relation to the previous TSN scheduling techniques, we employ constraint programming to devise a TSN schedule computation engine tailored to the needs of low-latency communication between IoT devices and VOs in converged IoT-cloud environments. Our proposed mechanism is compliant with TAS and addresses the dynamicity of cloud environments through the ability of rapid TSN schedule computation.

VII. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we presented a TAS-compliant scheduler to address the specific needs of IoT-VO communication in terms of bounded latency and rapid schedule computation, every time the IoT-VO association has changed or when a VO migrates to another host or edge cloud. The TSN scheduling problem at hand has been formulated and tackled using constraint programming.

The proposed TAS schedule model is validated in comparison to static TSN schedules, with both mechanisms prioritizing IoT-VO traffic over cross traffic on three topologies that encompass IoT and edge computing nodes (connected through TSN bridges). Our simulation results demonstrate significant gains both in terms of latency and jitter for high-priority

traffic handled by the proposed scheduler. The aspect for which our scheduling approach stands out is the ability to confine the deviation of latency and jitter values around their respective mean values, which is of paramount importance when dealing with scheduled traffic. At the same time, our TAS scheduler yields negligible execution time at the scale of our experimentation.

Future work will focus on evaluating the performance of the scheduler by employing general CP heuristics, *i.e.*, variable and value ordering heuristics during search, as well as symmetry breaking, both of which have been proven to have a large impact on the execution time of solvers. Furthermore, a research direction of high interest would be to integrate the TSN scheduling component into a higher-level orchestration setting, where decisions concern the placement of VOs to edge nodes, so that IoT-VO communication constraints are met.

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